

SOME PROBLEMS OF IMPROVING THE INVESTIGATION OF JUVENILE CRIMES

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Annotation: Crimes committed by minors are a serious problem that requires careful consideration and an integrated approach on the part of law enforcement agencies and society as a whole. This article analyzes the main problems and challenges faced in the investigation of juvenile crimes, as well as suggests possible ways to solve them.

Keywords: crime, investigation, minor, factors, problems of investigations.

In the modern world, the problem of juvenile delinquency remains one of the most acute challenges for society. Minors, being at the stage of forming their personality and values, may face various factors contributing to the commission of crimes. Therefore, the investigation of crimes committed by minors plays a key role in ensuring the safety of society and protecting the rights and interests of adolescents.

The investigation of juvenile delinquency has deep social significance, as it directly affects public well-being. Crimes committed by teenagers often have negative consequences for their victims, families and the surrounding community. This can have harmful effects on the mental and physical health of the victims, as well as on the economic development and social stability of society.

Crimes committed by minors are illegal acts committed by persons who have not reached the age of majority, the legal age (usually 18 years). These crimes have their own characteristics related to the age and psychological characteristics of the offenders, as well as a special legal regime aimed at their correction and social rehabilitation.

Juvenile crimes are socially dangerous acts provided for by criminal law, which are committed by persons under the age of 18. Depending on national legislation, the age at which criminal liability begins may vary (for example, in Uzbekistan – from 14 years for serious crimes, and from 16 years for less serious ones).

Crimes committed by minors can be classified on various grounds:

1. By the nature and degree of public danger:

o Crimes against the person (for example, murder, bodily injury, rape).

- o Crimes against property (e.g. theft, robbery, robbery).
- o Crimes in the field of economic activity (for example, fraud, extortion).
- o Crimes against public safety and order (e.g. hooliganism, vandalism).

2. Motivated by:

- o Mercenary crimes (aimed at obtaining material benefits).
- o Violent crimes (related to physical violence).
- o Anti-social crimes (related to violation of public order).

3. By the method of commission:

- o Individual crimes (committed by one person).
- o Group crimes (committed by a group of persons by prior agreement or by an organized group).

4. According to the circumstances of the commission:

- o Premeditated crimes (committed with direct intent).
- o Manslaughter (committed by negligence).

Features of criminal liability of minors

1. Age of criminal responsibility: as a rule, milder age limits are set.

2. Punishments and corrections: special educational measures aimed at social rehabilitation are applied, such as prevention, registration, referral to special educational institutions.

3. Lawsuits: They are considered in a special order, taking into account the psychophysical characteristics of minors and their social environment.

4. Social rehabilitation: emphasis on educational, psychological and social programs that help to adapt and prevent relapses.

The investigation of juvenile crimes plays an important role in protecting the rights and interests of adolescents. It ensures fair and impartial consideration of cases involving minors and provides an opportunity for adequate punishment or rehabilitation of guilty adolescents. It also helps to prevent possible consequences that may have a negative impact on the future development and adaptation of young people in society. An adequate response to crimes committed by young people helps to identify the risk factors and problems behind these actions and take measures to eliminate them. This may include psychological and social support, educational programs, and family and school involvement in the rehabilitation process.

The investigation of crimes committed by minors is an integral part of ensuring the safety of society. Effective counteraction to juvenile delinquency contributes to the creation of a safe and stable environment for all members of

society. This is important not only for the protection of individual citizens, but also for maintaining trust in justice and the law as a whole.

It is difficult to overestimate the importance of investigating juvenile crimes in modern society. This process plays a key role in ensuring the safety, protection of the rights and interests of adolescents, as well as the prevention and prevention of crime among young people. The development of effective approaches to the investigation of juvenile crimes remains an important priority for law enforcement agencies, social services and society as a whole.

Crimes committed by minors remain a serious problem that requires careful consideration and effective management. The investigation of these crimes is a complex process that faces a number of problems and challenges that may make it difficult to complete it successfully and punish the perpetrators.

When investigating crimes committed by minors, there are often problems with access to information. Information about teenagers, especially in the context of their criminal activities, may be limited by legal restrictions related to confidentiality and data protection. This makes it difficult to collect the necessary information for a complete and objective investigation.

Adolescents have special characteristics of psychology and behavior, which can make it difficult to determine their motivation for committing crimes. Often, young criminals act under the influence of various factors, such as the influence of the environment, peer pressure or personal problems, which requires special attention and analysis.

Effective investigation of juvenile crimes requires close cooperation between various institutions such as law enforcement agencies, educational institutions, social services and courts. However, there is often insufficient coordination and information exchange between these institutions, which makes it difficult to effectively investigate and take measures to prevent repeat crimes.

One of the key aspects of investigating juvenile crimes is the development of effective rehabilitation and re-socialization programs. However, many of the existing programs may not be sufficiently adapted to the characteristics of adolescents and may not provide the necessary support for their successful reintegration into society.

It is important to ensure that the rights and legitimate interests of minors are respected during the investigation of crimes. This includes protecting their privacy, providing access to adequate protection and a fair trial.

There are the main problems that law enforcement agencies face when investigating crimes committed by minors, and we will also suggest ways to solve them.

The main problems and challenges:

1. Insufficient understanding of the peculiarities of adolescent psychology and social dynamics: The investigation of juvenile crimes often faces the problem of understanding the motives and factors contributing to the commission of crimes by adolescents. It is necessary to take into account the peculiarities of adolescent development, their interaction with the environment, the influence of group dynamics and other factors influencing their decision-making.

2. Limited access to information and information about crimes: Unlike crimes committed by adults, information about juvenile crimes is often limited due to legal restrictions related to age and confidentiality. This creates difficulties in collecting and analyzing the data necessary for an effective investigation.

3. Insufficient coordination between law enforcement agencies and social services: The investigation of juvenile crimes requires cooperation between various institutions and organizations, including the police, the prosecutor's office, the court, social services, schools and medical institutions. However, there is often a lack of coordination and information exchange between them.

4. Issues of confidentiality and protection of the rights of adolescents during the investigation: It is important to ensure that the rights and legitimate interests of minors are respected during the investigation of crimes. This includes protecting their privacy, providing access to lawyers and social workers, and taking into account the specifics of their psychological state.

Ways to solve problems:

- The introduction of specialized education and training programs for law enforcement and social services personnel aimed at understanding the characteristics of adolescent psychology and effective methods of working with minors.

- Development of inter-institutional cooperation and information exchange between institutions involved in the investigation of juvenile crimes.

- Improvement of legislation and policy in the field of protection of the rights and interests of minors during the investigation of crimes.

The investigation of crimes committed by minors remains a complex and urgent issue for law enforcement agencies and society as a whole. Solving the

problems and challenges associated with this problem requires an integrated approach and joint efforts on the part of various institutions and public organizations. It is important to develop effective investigative strategies focused on the characteristics of adolescent psychology and social dynamics, as well as to ensure that the rights and interests of minors are respected during the entire investigation and rehabilitation process.

The problem of juvenile delinquency requires a comprehensive approach, including prevention, legal regulation, social rehabilitation and education. Taking into account the peculiarities of age and psychology, the legal system strives not only to punish, but also to correct juvenile offenders, helping them to become full-fledged members of society.

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